

Static dielectric constant of some pure protic and aprotic solvents and for binary solvent mixtures

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Abstract : The dielectric constant values of some protic and aprotic solvents in pure state are presented on the basis of MSA method, perturbation theory and Cluster expansion formulation. The calculations are made on statistical mechanical basis considering the cooperative effect and formation of cluster by H-bonding or dipole alignment. The results are compared with the experimental values. To calculate this for binary mixtures of some important mixed solvents we have to consider the partial molar volumes, which are calculated from a relation considering the hard sphere diameters and number density of the corresponding solvents. The results are compared with the experimental values and this agreement is found good.

Keywords : Dielectric constant, perturbation theory, cluster integral.

The dielectric constant of a liquid system is a physico-chemical property of major importance in chemistry. The statistical mechanical theory of dielectric constant was proposed by Kirkwood¹. Werthiem² solved this Kirkwood's classical electrostatic theory by Mean Spherical Approximation method³. This result showed that the dielectric constant is an increasing function of y , which is called the dipolar strength function of medium, i.e. $y = 4\pi\rho\mu^2/9kT$, where ρ = number density, μ = dipole moment, k = Boltzman constant, T = temperature. Thus the dielectric constant (ϵ) is given by the expression

$$\epsilon_{\text{MSA}} = \frac{(1+4\xi)^2 (1+\xi)^4}{(1-2\xi)^6} \quad (\text{A})$$

where,
$$\frac{(1+4\xi)^2}{(1-2\xi)^4} - \frac{(1-2\xi)^2}{(1+\xi)^4} = 3y$$

This equation showed that for $y = 0$, $\epsilon_{\text{MSA}} = 1$ and $y = \alpha$, $\epsilon_{\text{MSA}} = \alpha$. This result is found good for lower values of dielectric constant.

The perturbation theory developed by Weeks *et al.*⁴ and Verlet *et al.*⁵ considering a polar liquid system, i.e. system of hard sphere with point dipole. Later Tani *et*

*al.*⁶ modified this by developing the following equation

$$\epsilon_{\text{PER}} = 1 + 3y + 3y^2 + 3y^3 \{(9I_{\text{dd}\Delta}/16\pi^2) - 1\} + \dots \quad (\text{B})$$

where

$$9I_{\text{dd}\Delta} = \int_0^\alpha \int_0^\alpha \int_{r_{12}-r_{13}}^{r_{12}+r_{13}} \frac{3 \cos^2 \alpha_3 - 1}{r_{13}^2 r_{23}^2} x r_{12} g_y(r_{12}, r_{13}, r_{23}) dr_{12} dr_{13} dr_{23}$$

However they used superposition approximation method to solve $I_{\text{dd}\Delta}$ and obtained reasonably good results⁶. Later Szalai, Henderson and Chan⁷ combined the MSA theory with the perturbation results. According to them

$$\epsilon_{\text{p,m}} = \epsilon_{\text{MSA}} + 3y^3 \{(9I_{\text{dd}\Delta}/16\pi^2) - 1\} + \dots \quad (\text{C})$$

Table 1 shows the dielectric constant values of some liquids according to eq. (C). It shows that the dielectric constant values of some liquids like water, alcohol, amides, etc. vary widely from the experimental results, i.e. the combination of two above methods fails for protic solvents. In this paper we have considered the cooperative and autogonistic effects between the dipoles of the neighboring molecules when the molecules are close together due to either hydrogen bonding and/or parallel alignment

Table 1. Dielectric constant of some protic and aprotic solvents

σ = hard sphere diameter, ρ = number density, μ = dipole moment values, $\epsilon_{p,m}$ = dielectric constant from eq. (C), ϵ_{expt} = experimental values

Sl. no.	Solvents	σ^a (Å)	$\rho \times 10^{23}$	μ (Debye)	γ	$I_{dd\Delta}/\sigma^6$	ξ	$\epsilon_{p,m}$	ϵ_{expt}
1.	Water	2.67	0.334	1.84	3.837	20.27	0.156	70.56	78.54
2.	Fluorobenzene	5.3	0.0638	1.61	0.561	24.58	0.0539	3.82	-
3.	Chlorobenzene	5.61	0.059	1.70	0.5785	26.85	0.551	4.03	5.6
4.	Bromobenzene	5.72	0.0571	1.73	0.5804	28.63	0.0552	4.10	5.4
5.	Iodobenzene	5.92	0.0538	1.91	0.667	29.14	0.0612	4.89	4.6
6.	Pyridine	5.169	0.0745	2.23	1.258	26.5	0.0923	12.12	12.5
7.	Methyl bromide	4.324	0.105	2.00	1.425	22.69	0.0991	13.25	-
8.	Ethyl bromide	4.85	0.08	2.03	1.119	23.82	0.0861	9.31	9.4
9.	Propyl bromide	5.3	0.067	2.18	1.0759	25.69	0.0841	9.18	9.20
10.	Butyl bromide	5.668	0.057	2.23	0.967	26.75	0.0787	7.96	-
11.	Methyl iodide	4.573	0.099	1.66	0.926	24.62	0.0765	7.16	7.1
12.	Ethyl iodide	5.03	0.077	1.91	0.954	25.26	0.078	7.57	7.4
13.	Propyl iodide	5.747	0.063	2.04	0.89	32.08	0.0746	7.67	-
14.	Butyl iodide	5.81	0.055	2.12	0.839	27.93	0.0717	6.58	6.3
15.	Methyl chloride	4.156	0.109	1.95	1.392	21.74	0.0978	12.3	12.9
16.	Ethyl chloride	4.67	0.083	2.08	1.218	22.6	0.0906	10.27	-
17.	Propyl chloride	5.13	0.068	2.08	0.9982	23.92	0.0803	7.88	-
18.	Butyl chloride	5.534	0.057	2.08	0.8367	24.94	0.0715	6.24	9.6
19.	Methanol	3.835	0.148	1.90	1.8127	22.47	0.1125	19.86	33.7
20.	Ethanol	4.435	0.1028	1.65	0.9496	23.05	0.0777	7.249	25.07
21.	Propanol	5.02	0.0805	1.75	0.831	26.05	0.0712	6.2955	21.8
22.	Butanol	5.45	0.065	1.75	0.675	27.15	0.0617	4.86	17.5
23.	Pentanol	5.77	0.055	1.65	0.508	27.76	0.0499	3.514	13.9
24.	Hexanol	6.113	0.048	1.60	0.4169	28.49	0.0426	2.897	10.3
25.	Heptanol	6.424	0.042	1.55	0.342	29.05	0.0363	2.456	6.7
26.	Ethylene glycol	4.621	0.1077	2.28	1.9	27.46	0.1153	27.53	37.7
27.	Diethyl ether	5.388	0.057	1.15	0.256	23.42	0.0283	1.98	4.3
28.	Ethyl acetate	5.421	0.0611	1.79	0.664	25.12	0.0609	4.65	6.0
29.	Ammonia	3.255	0.2129	1.47	1.5615	21.17	0.1042	14.48	25.0
30.	Acetone	4.809	0.0816	2.85	2.25	23.72	0.1249	32.19	21.0
31.	Toluene	5.64	0.0565	0.375	0.0269	26.05	0.0034	1.085	2.4
32.	Chloroform	5.052	0.0748	1.1	0.3075	24.90	0.0332	2.245	5.05
33.	1,4-Dioxane	5.55	0.0702	0.45	0.0482	32.26	0.0059	1.15	2.209

^aRef. Table 3.

of the dipoles. So, some clusters of molecules are formed due to cooperative effect that changed the MSA and perturbation result considerably.

Method of calculation :

Pure solvent :

In this paper, the cluster integral method that was originally introduced by Mayer *et al.* and developed by

Jepson⁸, are adopted. We consider a system of hard sphere molecule having diameter σ and packing fraction $\eta =$

$\frac{\pi}{6} \rho \sigma^3$. The two-body correlation function of the order

of the inverse of volume is introduced. The system is considered in a uniform external electric field E_0 . Kirkwood showed that for grand canonical ensemble,

$$\frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} R^3 E_0 = \beta \int u_1(u_1 \cdot E_0) \rho_1(\{1\}) d\{1\} +$$

$$\beta \int u_1(u_2 \cdot E_0) \rho_2(\{1\}, \{2\}) d\{1,2\} \quad (1)$$

with $\rho_{(1)}(1) = \frac{1}{\Xi} \sum_N \frac{z^N}{(N-1)!} \int \dots \int \exp[-\beta V(\{N\})] d\{2 \dots N\}$

and $\rho_2(1,2) = \frac{1}{\Xi} \sum_N \frac{z^N}{(N-2)!} \int \dots \int \exp[-\beta V(\{N\})] d\{3 \dots N\}$

where the grand partition function

$$\Xi = \sum_N \frac{z^N}{N!} \int \dots \int \exp[-\beta V(\{N\})] d\{N\}$$

The first integral can be described as an average over all locations of the particle combined with an average over all orientations. Clearly after averaging over locations all orientations of the dipole are equally by symmetry. This makes the integration over orientations trivial. Comparing the result with the normalization integral obtained by dropping the u and E_0 factors, we see that this first term becomes,

$$\beta \int u_1(u_1 \cdot E_0) \rho_1(\{1\}) d\{1\} = \frac{1}{3} N \beta \mu^2 E_0 \quad (2)$$

We may combine eqs. (1) and (2) to give

$$(\epsilon - 1)/(\epsilon + 2) = y + A \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where } A = \frac{\beta}{R^3} \int \int (u_1 \cdot e)(u_2 \cdot e) \rho_2(\{1\}, \{2\}) d\{1,2\}$$

Here, N = total number of particles, V = volume, and E = unit vector in the direction of the field E_0 .

For a fluid system $\rho_{(2)}(\{1\}, \{2\})$ is related to the two-body correlation function $g(\{1\}, \{2\})$ and the potential of average force $w(\{1\}, \{2\})$ by the equations

$$\rho^{(2)}(1,2) = c^2 g(\{1\}, \{2\})$$

$$\text{and } g(\{1\}, \{2\}) = \exp[-\beta w(1,2)] \quad (4)$$

The lowest-order expression obtained for the term $w(1,2)$ in 1 when particles 1 and 2 are further apart than 2σ by summing diagrams which consist of chains of dipoles connected between the two particles in question.

$$w^{12}(1,2) = (-1/\epsilon_d) \mu_1 T_{12} \cdot \mu_2,$$

$$\text{and } T_{12} = (1/r_{12}^5)(3r_{12} r_{12} - U r_{12}^2) \quad (5)$$

where U is the unit tensor and ϵ_d is a dielectric constant between spherical dipolar molecules given by

$$\epsilon_d = 1/(1 + 2x)(1 - x) \quad (6)$$

Now, when two particles 1 and 2 come closer than 2σ , then A in eq. (3) has two contributions A_1 and A_2 . A_1 depends on the magnitude of the interparticle separation and given by

$$A_1 = 17x^3/16\epsilon_d \quad (7)$$

The second term is calculated for a finite volume contribution which is proportional to the reciprocal of the volume and gives non-vanishing contribution to macroscopic dielectric. This contribution is equal to

$$A_2 = -\frac{\beta^2 c^2}{R} \int \int (u_1 \cdot e)(u_2 \cdot e) S^{(1)}(\{1\}, \{2\}) d\{1\} d\{2\} \quad (8)$$

where $S^{(1)}(\{1\}, \{2\})$ are the potential of forces over the positions of particles 1 and 2. Jepson *et al.* solved the eq. (8) by a special calculation using Fourier transform techniques, and finally the result be $A_2 = -2x^3/(\epsilon d)^2$. However, this integral obtained from the lattice method has a strong dependence on the molecular diameter b which is chosen to be $(3/4\pi)(V/N)^{1/3}$. So finally, the expression for dielectric constant is

$$\epsilon_{cl} = (1 + 2x)/(1 - x) \quad (9)$$

where, $x = y + A_1 + A_2$.

In order to obtain the result, the following assumptions are made.

- (1) When $R < 2b$ then $x = y + A_1$
- (2) When $R > 2b$ then
 - (a) $R - b < 1.5$, $x = y - A_1 + A_2$
 - (b) $1.6 > R - b > 1.5$, $x = y + A_2$
 - (c) $R - b > 1.6$, $x = y + A_1 + A_2$

So, we consider that for protic solvents the cluster contribution should be added to the expression given by Szalai *et al.* Therefore,

$$\epsilon_{total} = \epsilon_{cl} + \epsilon_{p,m} \quad (10)$$

Calculations are made from eq. (10) with eq. (9) and eq. (C) for a number of protic and aprotic solvents and are tabulated in Table 2. The parameters used are given in Table 3.

Mixtures of solvents :

For calculation of the dielectric constant for the mix-

Table 2. Modified values for dielectric constant for protic solvents from cluster expansion method

ϵ_{cl} = from eq. (9), ϵ_{total} = from eq. (10), ϵ_{expt} = from literatures

Sl. no.	Solvent	A_1	A_2	x	ϵ_{cl}	ϵ_{total}	ϵ_{expt}
1.	Water	0.0210	0.0445	0.284	2.1899	72.75	78.54
2.	Methanol	0.1684	0.2989	0.721	8.753	28.61	32.7
3.	Ethanol	0.1329	0.0366	0.8532	18.436	25.68	25.07
4.	Propanol	0.2743	0.2323	0.789	12.218	18.52	21.8
5.	Butanol	0.2496	0.3588	0.785	11.954	16.82	17.5
6.	Pentanol	0.1382	0.2579	0.766	10.821	14.33	13.9
7.	Hexanol	0.0823	0.1657	0.6649	6.953	9.85	10.3
8.	Heptanol	0.0471	0.0982	0.487	3.848	6.30	6.7
9.	Ethylene glycol	0.1504	0.2754	0.651	6.596	34.13	37.7
10.	Diethyl ether	0.0200	0.0425	0.279	2.161	4.14	4.3
11.	Ammonia	0.2286	0.3532	0.765	10.766	25.25	25.0
12.	Toluene	0.00002	0.00004	0.0271	1.084	2.17	2.4
13.	Chloroform	0.0345	0.0727	0.3425	2.563	4.81	5.05
14.	1,4-Dioxane	0.0001	0.0002	0.0484	1.153	2.30	2.209

Table 3. Physical properties of some pure liquids

Temp. = 25 °C, Pressure = 1 atm

Sl. Name no.	Diameter ^a (Å)	Density ^{b,c} (g/cc)	Dielectric constant ^e	Dipole moment ^{a,d,c} (D)
1. Water	2.67	0.997	78.56	1.84
2. Acetonitrile	4.244	0.777	35.85	3.924
3. Methanol	3.835	0.787	32.6	1.90
4. Ethanol	4.435	0.788	24.3	1.65
5. Nitromethane	4.302	1.1313	36.7	
6. Tetrahydrofuran	5.07	0.8811	7.58	1.75
7. N,N-DMF	4.74	0.9443	36.71	3.86
8. 1,4-Dioxane	5.55	1.0269	2.209	0.45
9. N-Methylformamide	4.41	0.9976	182.4	3.83
10. Formamide	3.73	1.1292	109.5	3.73

^aD. Ben-Naim and Y. Marcus, 1993, 97, 7736.

^bInternational Critical Table, Mc-Graw Hill, New York, 1928, Vol. 3.

^cIndian J. Pure Appl. Phys., 1991, 29, 576.

^dCRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 71st ed., CRC Press, Inc, David R. Lide, 1990-91.

^eJ. Am. Chem. Soc., 1936, 58, 1482.

tures of two or more liquids, we approach in a different manner. For the theoretical calculation, Moreau and Douheret⁹ used Decroocq's simplified formula which is

$$\epsilon_m(x) = \epsilon(x) - (1 - \phi)\epsilon(0) + \phi\epsilon(1)$$

where ϕ denotes the volume fraction of solute. Now, in our system, we modify the above formula for ideal mix-

tures,

$$\epsilon_{mix} = (1 - \phi)\epsilon_0 + \phi\epsilon_1 \quad (11)$$

When the mixtures contains only two compositions 0 and 1. Here ϕ denotes the volume fraction of component 1,

$$\phi = xV_1 / \{(1 - x)V_0 + xV_1\} \quad (12)$$

where, x = mole fraction of component 1, V_0 = partial molar volume of component 0 in solvent 1 and V_1 = partial molar volume of component 1 in solvent 0.

Now, for a hard sphere mixtures, the PMV of a particular species in a solvent can be obtained by the following series of equations¹⁰; if the packing fraction of components 1 and 0 are ξ_1 and ξ_0 respectively, then

$$\xi_1 = (\pi/6)\rho_{mix}\sigma_1^3 \text{ and } \xi_0 = (\pi/6)\rho_{mix}\sigma_0^3$$

where ρ , σ are the corresponding number density and hard sphere diameter respectively. Now, if V'_1 and V'_0 are the molar volume of solvent 1 and 0 respectively, then

$$V_0/V'_1 = Y_1 \text{ and } V_0/V'_0 = Y_0$$

where $Y_1 = \text{factor} = C_1(x_1^3 + 3\alpha_1x_1^2 + 3\alpha_1\beta_1x_1 + 3\alpha_1\beta_1\gamma_1)$

Here $x_1 = \sigma_0/\sigma_1$; $\alpha_1 = (1 - \xi_1)/(1 + 2\xi_1)$;
 $\beta_1 = (1 - \xi_1)/(1 + 2\xi_1 - \xi_1^2)$;

$$\gamma_1 = (1 - \xi_1)/\xi_1;$$

$$C_1 = (1 + 3\alpha_1 + 3\alpha_1\beta_1 + \alpha_1\beta_1\gamma_1)^{-1}$$

Table 4. Determination of dielectric constants of some mixtures

Temp. = 298.15 K, Pressure = 1 atm

(a) For acetonitrile-water system :

Sl. no.	W_1	ρ (g/cc)	V_1	V_0	ϕ	ϵ_m	ϵ_{expt}
1.	0	0.9971	11.462	48.505	0	78.54	78.54
2.	22.08	0.9580	12.318	45.570	0.315	65.09	69.22
3.	53.6	0.8833	14.738	40.739	0.584	53.63	53.96
4.	66.48	0.8543	16.011	38.669	0.678	49.61	48.30
5.	75.91	0.8311	17.093	37.073	0.750	46.52	44.53
6.	85.16	0.8098	18.268	35.492	0.830	43.09	41.07
7.	90.24	0.7981	18.980	34.608	0.881	40.93	39.21
8.	95.08	0.7882	19.693	33.773	0.936	38.59	37.60
9.	97.08	0.7857	19.982	33.449	0.961	37.53	36.86
10.	99.32	0.7799	20.358	33.038	0.991	36.256	36.25

W_1 = weight % of acetonitrile; ϵ_{expt} = *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 401.

(b) For acetonitrile-methanol system :

Sl. no.	W_1	ρ (g/cc)	V_1	V_0	ϕ	ϵ_m	ϵ_{expt}
1.	0	0.78655	41.224	50.9858	0	32.63	32.63
2.	14	0.787	41.353	50.8431	0.135	33.09	33.04
3.	14.7	0.78703	41.360	50.8359	0.142	33.11	33.15
4.	17.2	0.78696	41.384	50.8091	0.166	33.19	33.25
5.	30.7	0.78682	41.517	50.6632	0.297	33.63	33.78
6.	34.2	0.7859	41.557	50.6195	0.331	33.75	33.78
7.	48.4	0.78438	41.7089	50.4523	0.470	34.22	34.16
8.	64.6	0.78244	41.8903	50.2543	0.631	34.76	34.44
9.	66.3	0.78198	41.9112	50.2316	0.648	34.82	34.96
10.	67.8	0.78179	41.9285	50.2128	0.663	34.87	34.70
11.	73.49	0.7812	41.9939	50.1417	0.721	35.07	35.12
12.	82.3	0.7797	42.1003	50.0263	0.812	35.37	35.47
13.	85.5	0.77932	42.1387	49.9848	0.845	35.49	35.52
14.	90.66	0.7784	42.2029	49.9155	0.8996	35.67	35.64
15.	94.67	0.7771	42.2566	49.8576	0.942	35.82	35.12
16.	100	0.77686	42.3207	49.7886	1	36.01	36.01

W_1 = weight % of acetonitrile; ϵ_{expt} = *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 1182.

(c) For acetonitrile-ethanol system :

Sl. no.	W_1	ρ (g/cc)	V_1	V_0	ϕ	ϵ_m	ϵ_{expt}
1.	0	0.7851	58.08722	52.9863	0	24.30	24.30
2.	8.47	0.785	58.1112	52.9634	0.086	25.30	25.21
3.	29.82	0.7844	58.1697	52.9078	0.303	27.79	27.41
4.	50.31	0.7827	58.2211	52.8590	0.508	30.16	29.50
5.	70.48	0.7806	58.2691	52.8134	0.708	32.48	31.96
6.	78.15	0.7796	58.2865	52.7970	0.784	33.36	32.94
7.	89.79	0.7768	58.3086	52.7760	0.900	34.69	34.55
8.	97.94	0.7771	58.3308	52.7550	0.980	35.61	35.60

W_1 = weight. % of acetonitrile; ϵ_{expt} = *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 401.

Table-4 (contd.)

(d) For water-ethanol system :

Sl. no.	W_1	ρ (g/cc)	V_1	V_0	ϕ	ϵ_m	ϵ_{expt}
1.	66.02	0.8730	14.834	41.6596	0.681	41.60	39.44
2.	76.66	0.8480	16.2757	39.3715	0.757	37.50	34.29
3.	84.02	0.8301	17.4271	37.7338	0.817	34.24	30.94
4.	90	0.8140	18.4941	36.3504	0.874	31.14	28.20
5.	96.08	0.7961	19.7277	34.8972	0.944	27.32	26.07
6.	97.11	0.7937	19.9421	34.6594	0.958	26.57	25.60
7.	98.09	0.7911	20.1549	34.4275	0.972	25.83	25.18
8.	99.1	0.7880	20.3851	34.1811	0.986	25.04	24.70

W_1 = weight % of water; $\epsilon_{\text{expt}} = J. Phys. Chem., 1969, 73, 401.$

(e) For acetonitrile-nitromethane system :

Sl. no.	W_1	ρ (g/cc)	V_1	V_0	ϕ	ϵ_m	ϵ_{expt}
1.	0	1.1246	93.9268	52.3293	0	36.00	36.00
2.	30.1	0.99325	92.6794	52.3207	0.265	35.96	36.01
3.	31.2	0.98872	92.6705	52.3207	0.276	35.96	36.07
4.	31.7	0.98696	92.6381	52.3205	0.280	35.96	35.93
5.	60.9	0.88498	91.9446	52.3156	0.569	35.91	35.96
6.	64.4	0.87453	91.8298	52.3148	0.605	35.92	35.65
7.	65.6	0.8708	91.8139	52.3147	0.618	35.91	35.98

W_1 = weight % of acetonitrile; $\epsilon_{\text{expt}} = J. Phys. Chem., 1964, 68, 1182.$

(f) For nitromethane-methanol system :

Sl. no.	W_1	ρ (g/cc)	V_1	V_0	ϕ	ϵ_m	ϵ_{expt}
1.	34.4	0.88057	40.8340	52.2397	0.2604	33.04	32.2
2.	37.3	0.88914	40.8669	52.2024	0.2851	33.14	32.24
3.	37.5	0.88988	40.8685	52.2006	0.2869	33.14	32.42
4.	38.1	0.89173	40.8751	52.1931	0.2921	33.17	32.2
5.	65.2	0.98126	41.2335	51.7891	0.5526	34.21	32.92
6.	69	0.99513	41.2928	51.7226	0.5941	34.38	33.01
7.	72.4	1.00781	41.3484	51.6605	0.6324	34.52	33.05
8.	92.2	1.0888	41.7174	51.2498	0.8840	35.54	34.74
9.	12.3	1.08952	41.7183	51.2488	0.8854	35.54	34.84
10.	93	1.09251	41.7336	51.2319	0.8954	35.58	34.91

W_1 = weight % of nitromethane; $\epsilon_{\text{expt}} = J. Phys. Chem., 1964, 68, 1182.$

(g) For *p*-dioxane-water system :

Sl. no.	W_1	ρ (g/cc)	V_1	V_0	ϕ	ϵ_m	ϵ_{expt}
1.	0	0.9971	50.2188	92.012	0	78.3	78.3
2.	20.0	1.0143	36.1018	84.9521	0.107	70.13	63.5
3.	40.0	1.0284	18.3828	76.7688	0.363	50.70	44.4
4.	60.0	1.0360	8.4031	67.0461	0.710	24.28	27.5
5.	80.0	1.035	8.4459	55.3310	0.843	14.18	12.1
6.	100.0	1.0269	15.5684	41.1357	1	2.209	2.209

W_1 = weight % of *p*-dioxane; $\epsilon_{\text{expt}} = J. Phys. Chem., 1964, 68, 1964.$

(h) For DMF-water system (at 298.15 K) :

Sl. no.	W_{water}	ρ (g/cc) ^a	V_{water}	V_{DMF}	ϕ	ϵ_m
1.	0	0.997	15.8685	62.8161	0	78.54
2.	1.724	0.9961	15.3361	62.4425	0.0173	77.80
3.	2.919	0.996	15.0079	62.1959	0.030	77.27
4.	7.072	0.9964	14.0139	61.3479	0.076	75.30
5.	9.002	0.9965	13.6114	60.9454	0.098	74.34
6.	14.51	0.9972	12.6785	59.785	0.165	71.51
7.	19.28	0.9964	12.0851	58.7158	0.222	69.05
8.	24	0.9948	11.7002	57.6107	0.277	66.71
9.	34.27	0.9948	11.4946	55.1907	0.382	62.25
10.	49.77	0.9876	12.4754	51.0631	0.5	57.20
11.	64.63	0.9766	14.593	46.6134	0.590	53.36
12.	79.21	0.9651	17.7339	41.7692	0.689	49.14
13.	86.38	0.9506	19.9321	39.0346	0.754	46.36
14.	100	0.9442	25.4801	33.7916	1	35.85

 W_{water} = weight % of water; ^a = *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1977, 50, 2229.

(i) For DMF-water system (at 308.15 K) :

Sl. no.	W_{water}	ρ (g/cc) ^a	V_{water}	V_{DMF}	ϕ	ϵ_m
1.	0	0.994	15.7498	62.7354	0	78.54
2.	1.724	0.9929	15.2199	62.3568	0.017	77.80
3.	2.919	0.9923	14.8815	62.0971	0.030	77.26
4.	6.179	0.9915	14.074	61.4044	0.066	75.72
5.	9.002	0.991	13.4775	60.8011	0.099	74.31
6.	15.82	0.9896	12.3826	59.3044	0.181	70.79
7.	20.06	0.9881	11.9268	58.3313	0.232	68.63
8.	23.98	0.9861	11.6495	57.3974	0.277	66.72
9.	33.82	0.986	11.5017	55.0873	0.376	62.48
10.	49.13	0.9797	12.4783	51.0554	0.493	57.48
11.	65.25	0.9678	14.8028	46.2445	0.591	53.30
12.	80.01	0.9552	18.0734	41.3166	0.693	48.96
13.	86.38	0.9454	20.0110	38.9446	0.753	46.41
14.	100	0.9414	25.5304	33.7526	1	35.85

 W_{water} = weight % of water; ^a = *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1977, 50, 2229.

(j) For tetrahydrofuran-water system (at 298.15 K) :

Sl. no.	W_{water}	ρ (g/cc) ^b	V_{water}	V_{THF}	ϕ	ϵ_m
1.	0	0.9971	27.7349	73.8007	0	78.54
2.	0.05	0.9885	16.6697	68.8741	0.179	65.86
3.	0.1	0.9797	11.7019	64.7504	0.381	51.52
4.	0.15	0.971	9.95140	61.2335	0.521	41.60
5.	0.2	0.96	9.6756	58.1182	0.600	35.95
6.	0.25	0.951	10.0672	55.4365	0.647	32.61
7.	0.3	0.9432	10.7390	53.0920	0.679	30.33
8.	0.35	0.9363	11.5251	51.0219	0.704	28.55
9.	0.4	0.9298	12.3559	49.1714	0.726	27.00

Table-4 (contd.)

10.	0.45	0.9239	13.1949	47.5133	0.746	25.56
11.	0.5	0.9184	14.0285	46.0163	0.766	24.16
12.	0.55	0.9135	14.8468	44.6639	0.786	22.75
13.	0.6	0.909	15.6492	43.4336	0.806	21.32
14.	0.65	0.905	16.4330	42.3129	0.827	19.85
15.	0.7	0.9012	17.2025	41.2831	0.848	18.33
16.	0.75	0.8976	17.9578	40.3340	0.870	16.75
17.	0.8	0.8942	18.6995	39.4570	0.894	15.10
18.	0.85	0.8911	19.4259	38.6466	0.918	13.36
19.	0.9	0.8881	20.1409	37.8923	0.944	11.54
20.	0.95	0.8852	20.8448	37.1888	0.971	9.61
21.	1.00	0.8821	21.5436	36.5259	1	7.58

W_{water} = weight % of water; b = *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1969, 52, 2349.

Similarly, $Y_0 = \text{factor} = C_0(x_0^3 + 3\alpha_0x_0^2 + 3\alpha_0\beta_0x_0 + 3\alpha_0\beta_0\gamma_0)$,

and also $x_0 = \sigma_1/\sigma_0$; $\alpha_0 = (1 - \xi_0)/(1 + 2\xi_0)$;
 $\beta_0 = (1 - \xi_0)/(1 + 2\xi_0 - \xi_0^2)$;

$\gamma_1 = (1 - \xi_0)/\xi_0$;

$C_0 = (1 + 3\alpha_0 + 3\alpha_0\beta_0 + \alpha_0\beta_0\gamma_0)^{-1}$

We took the following systems to calculate the dielectric constant by the above equations and compared the results with the experimental values. The Tables (a-j) shows the results for dielectric constant for mixed solvent systems at varying composition.

Results and discussion

The calculation of dielectric constant values of some common solvents according to eq. (C) are made and given in Table 1 with the physical and chemical parameters used for the above calculations given in Table 2. This equation indicates that dielectric constant values depend very much on the polarity of the liquid though practical experiments show that the dipole moment or polarity has no direct correlation with dielectric constant. As for example, acetonitrile has $\mu = 3.92$ debye, where $\epsilon_{\text{expt}} = 36.7$, whereas methyl formamide has $\mu = 3.86$ debye but has highest dielectric constant at room temperature. However, it also be found that the above equation is not suitable for compounds having $\mu > 2$ debye; as at high μ value, y becomes very large and correspondingly the equation converge very poorly. Therefore, solvents that have $\mu < 2$ debye have been taken in consideration.

From the Table 1, it is found that the results for aprotic solvents (sl. no. 2 to 18) are in close agreement with the experimental values. However, for protic solvents (sl.

no. 1 and 19 to 33) the calculated values are much lower than that of experiment.

Hence, the cooperative and autogonistic effects between the dipoles of the neighboring molecules are considered to explain this discrepancy when the molecules are close together due to hydrogen bonding or parallel alignment of dipoles. The alcohols show regularly changing properties as the aliphatic chain length is increased as the numbers of hydroxyl-groups are increased. The freezing properties and the dipole moment do not show this regularity but the entropy change on freezing shows this regularity with increasing size and flexibility of the molecules¹¹. The dielectric constant drops as the chain length increases in alcohols but increases with the increasing number of hydroxyl groups.

Therefore, the cluster expansion method is suitable for there after calculations of the dielectric constant. The original cluster method derived by Mayer considering the nature of hydrogen bonding and correlation was modified by Jepson *et al.*⁸. The force between two charged spherical ions in a dipolar system have been calculated. If the spheres are considered large this gives a method for obtaining the dielectric constant. Jepson applied the cluster method to the standard formula for dielectric constant expressing the moment of the solvent of the sample in terms of correlation between two dipoles in a sphere of material, Hence, the total dielectric constant is the summation of ϵ_{cl} and $\epsilon_{p,m}$ and shown in Table 2.

Here, we slightly modify the above equation for $y > 1$; in this case we use y' ($y' = 1/y$) instead of y to avoid the negative sign. Now, we see that the results almost tally with that of experimental values except for water and chlorine-containing compounds. A slightly lower value

is still found there. The high electro negativity property of chlorine atom may increase the experimental values of dielectric constant of corresponding chlorine-containing compounds than that of theoretical values.

However, in case of water the reason behind this discrepancy is still unknown. This may be due to the variation of determining hard sphere diameter water. One point should be mentioned in this context that the hard sphere diameter is an important parameter for calculations. There are several methods of calculations for hard sphere diameter. Though the X-ray scattering data is considered to be ideal in many cases, the data of most of the compounds are not still available. The solubility data, surface tension/parachor or molar volume data are easily available. It has been found that solubility data of gases in the liquid can be used for calculations. It has also been found that the hard sphere diameter obtained from the above mentioned method couldn't explain the large variation of the dielectric constant of the hydrophobic solvents. The various methods of calculations of hard sphere diameter leads to quite close values but some physical parameters like compressibility, heat of vapourisation etc. depends largely on the hard sphere diameter whereas dielectric constant itself does not depend much on the hard sphere diameter. However in case of mixture of different components the

variation of dielectric constant on mole fraction of a component depends on the partial molar volume and so on of the hard sphere diameter.

For mixed solvents the calculated dielectric constant values agree well with the experimental results. However for water-ethyl alcohol system results are still not good. This work is in progress.

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